

MICROSCOPIC INNER MATERIALS DAMAGE DUE TO
TWO LEVEL FATIGUE IN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Two level fatigue loading (two stage loading) is applied on the carbonfiber composites by changing the sequence of levels, during which the inner materials damage is investigated quantitatively through the microscopic approach, mostly by use of optical tools. It is observed that the fatigue lifetime depends on the sequence of fatigue loading levels and on the microscopic inner materials damage. The microscopic inner materials damage observed experimentally is an increasing function of fatigue cycles. The degradation of stiffness and strength is also measured to be correlated with the cycles.

INTRODUCTION

During the past research works by the present authors [1], it was found that the microscopic inner materials damage such as the transverse cracking, the interlaminar delamination and the fiber fracture were influential to the materials degradation resulting in the decrease in stiffness and strength. In the present research work, two level fatigue loading is performed by changing the sequence of loading levels, and the microscopic inner materials damage is measured through optical tools to be correlated with the fatigue cycles and to be explained for the two level fatigue fracture behavior. The degradation of stiffness and strength is also measured as a function of fatigue cycles during two level fatigue loading. Microscopic quantitative work as to two level fatigue is quite

an unexplored one especially for composites.

SPECIMEN AND FATIGUE LOADING

Specimen

As shown in Figure 1, 8-ply cross laminates of carbon/epoxy composites with the fiber weight content of 59.4 %, cured at 120°C for an hour, manufactured by Toray Industries, Japan were employed. The fiber direction is $0^\circ / \pm 45^\circ / 90^\circ$, symmetrical.

Figure 1. Carbon/epoxy composite specimen (Unit in mm)

S - N curve

The fatigue stress amplitude in terms of the number of cycles at fracture was obtained as shown in Figure 2 as the S-N curve, in which σ_{\max} is a total amplitude, σ_B is a breaking stress and N_f is a cycle at fracture, i.e., lifetime. The fatigue loading was applied by a Shimadzu Servopulser hydraulic fatigue tester made in Japan in a sinusoidal wave with a stress ratio of zero at 5 Hz at room temperature.

Figure 2. S - N curve

STIFFNESS AND STRENGTH DEGRADATION

As for the two level fatigue loading purpose two fatigue stress amplitude cases were chosen, i.e., $\sigma_{\max} / \sigma_B = 0.8$ at $N_f = 36800$ cycles and $\sigma_{\max} / \sigma_B = 0.95$ at $N_f = 340$ cycles.

In Figure 3, the stiffness degradation is shown, in which E is the Young's modulus, E_0 the initial Young's modulus, n_1 / N_1 the fractional fatigue life spent at the first stage, n_2 / N_2 also at the second stage, and L and H indicate the lower ($\sigma_{\max} / \sigma_B = 0.8$) and higher ($\sigma_{\max} / \sigma_B = 0.95$) levels, respectively, while L - H and H - L indicate the sequence of levels. The second stage starts from $n_1 / N_1 = 0.5$. It is recognized that a 0.8 stress amplitude case in the first stage is always below that of 0.95, and a L - H case shows the immediate fatigue fracture just after switching to the higher level of H.

While for the strength degradation shown in Figure 4, the similar experimental tendency is observed, in which σ_R is the strength.

all the data shown in Figures 3 and 4 were obtained at room temperature.

Figure 3. Stiffness degradation

Figure 4. Strength degradation

DAMAGE CURVES

The damage curves showing the fractional lifetimes for two level cycling for carbonfiber composites are shown in Figure 5. For comparison, theoretical curves by Palmgren and Miner [2] and by Hashin and Rotem [3] are also shown in Figure 5. The Palmgren and Miner rule is given by

$$\frac{n_1}{N_1} + \frac{n_2}{N_2} = 1$$

for the lifetime in two level cyclic loading σ_1 for n_1 cycles and σ_2 for n_2 cycles, where N_1 and N_2 are the lifetimes for constant σ_1 and σ_2 stress amplitude cycling respectively as give by an S-N curve. Also for the Hashin and Rotem postulate

$$\left(\frac{n_1}{N_1} \right)^{\frac{\log N_2}{\log N_1}} + \frac{n_2}{N_2} = 1$$

is given for the lifetime estimation.

Figure 5. Damage curves

In view of Figure 5, it is observed that the enhanced nonlinearity of two level cycling data is shown. These experimental data, though rather a few plotting, however, are also supported by those of Broutman and Sahu for the glassfiber composites [4], in which the theoretical values of Miner's sum using the linear residual strength hypothesis range from 1.03 to 1.36 for the H-L case and 0.32 to 0.96 for the L-H case. The agreement between the experimental data and the Hashin and Rotem postulate seems to be poor, due to the strong nonlinearity of obtained data. The general tendency of two level cycling of carbonfiber composites can be acceptable.

MICROSCOPIC APPROACH

Microscopic inner materials damage factors employed here are selected with the aid of previous report [1], and they are as follows. [5]

Transverse cracking density

Total transverse crack length a_T divided by the scanning area A_T , as shown in Figure 6. $A_T = 10 \text{ mm} \times 1.15 \text{ mm}$ thickness, for 3 lengthwise thickness sections, cut by an diamond cutter.

Figure 6. Transverse cracking density
(400 X microscope is used.)

In Figure 6, L-H loading shows more transverse cracking leading toward very short lifetime after switching to the higher level of H. To the contrary, H-L loading shows longer fatigue lifetime compared to L-H case. These reasons may be explained as follows; for L-H loading just after switching to higher level of H, the transverse cracking density already exceeds the very value obtained in the first stage of single level loading of H as shown by dotted lines denoting a critical value leading toward fracture, hence almost immediate fracture of L-H case after switching to H level could be explained. The similar understanding may be valid for H-L case showing the longer lifetime after switching to L level, of which fracture happens, when the transverse cracking density reaches the maximum failure value of single level loading of L only, in the second stage.

Interlaminar delamination ratio

Total delamination length a_d divided by the total scanning interlaminar length in the lengthwise thickness section L_T , as shown in Figure 7. $L_T = 40 \text{ mm} \times 7$ laminate interfaces; cut by a diamond cutter, 5 places, along the width.

Figure 7. Interlaminar delamination ratio
(400 X microscope is used.)

In view of Figure 7, L-H case shows the immediate fracture after switching to H level, which is well understood that the immediate a_d / L_T value beginning in the second stage already far exceeds that of H single stage only. However, for H-L case, the above explanation does not hold so far as the present test results are concerned.

Fiber fracture ratio

Total fiber fracture number n_b divided by the scanning fiber number N_T , shown in Figure 8, obtained for 0° fiber within a scanning area for 5 places alongside the specimen length. In order to count 0° fiber number, the deply method [6] was employed to burn off the resin at 450°C for an hour, so as to easily count the fiber by an optical microscope. In view of Figure 8, the immediate fracture after switching to H level in the L-H case can be explained by the same reason already described in the two preceding microscopic damage factors, but the behavior of H-L case is not yet duly explained by the obtained results.

Figure 8. Fiber fracture ratio. (400 X microscope is used.)

CONCLUSIONS

Two level fatigue is performed on the carbonfiber composites. The effects of sequence of levels are also investigated in combination with the microscopic inner materials damage factors such as the transverse cracking, the interlaminar delamination and the fiber fracture, all of which are measured quantitatively by an optical microscope. The L-H case could explain its immediate fracture occurring just after starting the second stage in correlation with all the microscopic inner materials damage factors, but not for the H-L case. Further investigation shall be done in this connection. The stiffness and strength degradation curves are also obtained in the present two level fatigue.

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